

A solution study of copper(II)-dipeptide complexation with tyrosinate and lysinate as bridging residues

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In order to infer upon the selective action of biological macromolecular parameters, like proteins, a pH-metric titration technique together with some supporting calorimetric and spectroscopic (UV-visible) studies have been made on complexation of copper(II) with dipeptides, such as, L-phenylalanyl-L-tyrosine (Phe-Tyr) and L-lysyl-L-tyrosine (Lys-Tyr) in solution at 25°C ($I = 0.1 M$, KNO_3). In dilute aqueous solution, in addition to metal-ligand coordination property of a simple dipeptide, there is interaction between copper(II) and the side chain phenolate group of the tyrosine residue and/or the ϵ -amino group of lysine residue. In all dimeric species, both the lysine and the tyrosine moieties may behave as bridges between monomeric complexes.

The interactions of transition metal ions with biomolecules like proteins, DNA, RNA, etc. have been reported to be one of the fundamental aspects of biochemical processes in living organisms¹⁻⁵. The involvement of the side-chain phenolate group of the tyrosine residue and the role of the lysyl residue in metal complexes of oligopeptides has not been extensively explored⁶⁻⁹.

In our present investigation, the complexation of copper(II) with model dipeptides of Tyr and Phe or Lys, such as, L-phenylalanyl-L-tyrosine (Phe-Tyr) and L-lysyl-L-tyrosine (Lys-Tyr), has been considered and detailed equilibrium study has been carried out over a wide range of pH. Further, UV-vis spectroscopic measurements have also been made to justify the mode of bonding in these complexes and selective action of peptides in biological systems.

Materials and methods :

The dipeptides were high purity products (Sigma) and were used without further purification. All other chemicals like copper(II) nitrate, potassium nitrate, etc., used were extra pure Merck products.

Sample solutions, each containing required molar ratio of metal ion, the ligand, HNO_3 (to adjust the initial pH) and KNO_3 (to adjust ionic strength, of 0.1 M), were titrated pH-metrically with standard NaOH, in the pH range 3.0–11.0 in a thermostated potentiometric vessel (25°C). The concentrations of the ligands in the sample were kept $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ or $2 \times 10^{-3} M$, the metal ion-ligand ratio was kept 1 : 1, 1 : 2 or 1 : 4 maintaining ionic strength $I = 0.1 M$ (KNO_3). The titrations were carried out in the above pH-range using 0.1 M NaOH.

Table 1. Thermodynamic parameters of dipeptide protonation at 25°C and $I = 0.1 M$ (KNO_3)

Dipeptide	Donor group	log K	$-\Delta H^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^0 (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
Phe-Tyr	-COOH (-COO)	3.21	2.1	18.3	54.2
	-NH ₃ ⁺ (-NH ₂)	7.24	38.4	41.3	9.7
	-OH (-O)	10.02	40.1	57.1	57.1
	-OH (-O)*	10.01	–	–	–
Lys-Tyr	-COOH (-COO ⁻)	3.04	1.9	17.3	51.5
	-NH ₃ ⁺ (-NH ₂)	7.39	39.0	42.1	10.5
	-OH (-O)	9.68	41.0	55.2	47.6
	ϵ -NH ₃ ⁺ (ϵ -NH ₂)	11.03	48.3	62.9	49.3
-OH (-O)*	9.71	–	–	–	

*Determined spectrophotometrically.

The protonation constants and modes of binding in complexes have been determined in metal ion-dipeptide systems spectrophotometrically in the UV-vis regions. The thermodynamic parameters have been estimated through calorimetric measurements and using the equilibrium constant data. The concentration stability constants $\beta_{pqr} = [M_p A_q H_r] / [M]P[A]^q[H]^r$, have been computed by standard method¹⁰.

Results and discussion

Dipeptide protonation :

The dipeptides under investigation Phe-Tyr and Lys-Tyr contain three and four dissociable protons, respectively, in the measurable pH-range. From the values of protonation constants and thermodynamic parameters, it is evident that

pH-metric and spectroscopic values for the tyrosine phenolic group are in close agreement within the experimental error. It is worth noticeable that deprotonation processes are almost entirely entropic and consist of a charge separation followed by large scale reorganisation of the solvent around the reacting partners. However, the log *K* value of the lysyl ε-NH₃⁺ group is high, which has been interpreted due to some electrostatic and/or non-covalent hydrophobic interactions between the tyrosyl and lysyl residues.

Cu^{II} dipeptide systems :

The Cu^{II}-dipeptide complex formation constants together with the thermodynamic parameters have been reported in Table 2. The formation constants of the Cu^{II} complexes of the ligand HA⁻ have also been calculated. The phenolic hydroxy does not dissociate in the pH-range of metal complex formation, hence HA⁻ may be regarded as the complex formation species. The calorimetric data are in the favour of thermodynamic stability of various metal dipeptide species.

For Cu^{II}-Phe-Tyr system, the species distribution curves (Fig. 1) show that there is formation of [Cu(HA)]⁺ species in the lower pH-range and its concentration becomes maximum at pH ~4. Now, there is simultaneous formation of

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves for the system Cu^{II}-Phe-Tyr as a function of pH (*C_M* = 0.004 M, *C_L* = 0.008 M).

[Cu(A)] which becomes maximum at pH ~5.5 and stays longer in a wide pH-range showing its high stability. In due course of titration, other species, [Cu(HA)(HAH₁)⁻], [Cu(AH₁)⁻], [Cu₂(AH₁)₂]²⁻ and [Cu(AH₂)₂]²⁻ appear in significant concentrations in the higher pH-range. It is, therefore, concluded that a peptide molecule HA co-ordinates through its terminal amino and peptide carbonyl (O-coordinated) groups, while HAH₁ means a molecule coordinates through its terminal amino and deprotonated peptide amide (N-coordinated) groups in higher pH-range.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters of Cu^{II}-dipeptide complex formation at 25°C and *I* = 0.1 M (KNO₃)*

Equilibria	-log <i>K</i>	log <i>B</i>	Δ <i>H</i> ⁰ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>G</i> ⁰ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>S</i> ⁰ (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
Phe-Tyr - Cu ^{II} :					
Cu ²⁺ + HA ⁻ ⇌ [Cu(HA)] ⁺	1.67	15.12	38.4	9.5	96.9
[Cu(HA)] ⁺ ⇌ [CuA] + H ⁺	3.56	11.51	49.4	20.3	97.7
[CuA] ⇌ [Cu(AH ₁) ⁻] + H ⁺	9.18	2.38	105.9	52.4	179.7
[Cu(AH ₁) ⁻] ⇌ [Cu(AH ₂) ₂] ²⁻ + H ⁺	10.42	7.46	172.3	59.5	378.5
2[Cu(AH ₁) ⁻] ⇌ [Cu ₂ (AH ₁) ₂] ²⁻	1.8	6.62	123.8	10.3	380.8
Lys-Tyr-Cu ^{II} :					
Cu ²⁺ + H ₂ A ⇌ [Cu(H ₂ A)] ²⁺	2.05	5.20	46.2	11.7	115.8
[Cu(H ₂ A)] ²⁺ ⇌ [Cu(HA)] ⁺ + H ⁺	3.78	22.36	64.0	21.6	142.5
[Cu(HA)] ⁺ ⇌ [CuA] + H ⁺	9.21	13.24	118.7	52.6	222.0
[CuA] ⇌ [Cu(AH ₁) ⁻] + H ⁺	9.72	3.62	59.4	55.5	13.4
[Cu(AH ₁) ⁻] ⇌ [Cu(AH ₂) ₂] ²⁻ + H ⁺	11.14	7.48	52.0	63.6	38.7
2[CuA] ⇌ [Cu ₂ A ₂]	3.65	28.24	125.9	20.8	352.6

* Uncertainty in Δ*H*⁰ ± 0.5 kJ mol⁻¹ and in Δ*S*⁰ ± 1 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

The deprotonation and coordination of the peptide-NH and, thus the formation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{HAH}_{-1})]$ is favoured by the interaction between the empty d -orbital of Cu^{II} and the 6π -electron system of the aromatic rings¹¹. Further, the appearance of a charge-transfer band at 380 nm has supported the formation of a cyclic dimer having composition $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{AH}_{-1})_2]^{2-}$ in which monomers $[\text{Cu}(\text{HAH}_{-1})]$ are linked through phenolate bridges.

The other dipeptide studied is Lys-Tyr which contains an extra acidic proton on the ϵ -amino group ($\epsilon\text{-NH}_3^+$) and it dissociates along with phenolic group only at $\text{pH} > 10$. The formation constants ($\log \beta_{\text{pqr}}$) of Cu^{II} -Lys-Tyr complexes of this ligand in the form of H_2A together with the thermodynamic parameters have been calculated (Table 2). The variation in concentrations of various species and their relative proportions at different pH have been depicted in Fig. 2. The species $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{A})]^{2+}$ formed in highly acidic medium is simultaneously converted into highly stable $[\text{Cu}(\text{HA})]^+$ species in the pH range 5.5–7.5. In the higher pH-range the formation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{A})]$, its dimerisation into $[\text{Cu}_2\text{A}_2]$ and thereafter its deprotonation to give $[\text{CuAH}_{-1}]^-$ and $[\text{CuAH}_{-2}]^{2-}$ complexes have been observed.

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves for the system Cu^{II} -Lys-Tyr as a function of pH ($C_M = 0.004 \text{ M}$, $C_L = 0.008 \text{ M}$).

The UV-visible spectroscopic results are such that maximum absorption occurs for major species $[\text{Cu}(\text{HA})]^+$ ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 623 \text{ nm}$, $\epsilon = 95$ at $\text{pH} \sim 6.7$); $[\text{CuA}]$ and $[\text{Cu}_2\text{A}_2]$ ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 613 \text{ nm}$, $\epsilon = 90$ at $\text{pH} \sim 9.5$) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{AH}_{-1})]^-$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{AH}_{-2})]^{2-}$ ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 621 \text{ nm}$, $\epsilon = 80$ at $\text{pH} \sim 11.5$). These results together with equilibrium data indicate the same mode of bonding in the corresponding species.

The dimer formation tendency of Lys containing dipeptide of tyrosine is slightly different, which may be due to strong Cu^{II} - Cu^{II} interaction. This can be seen from the intensity of charge transfer band at 374 nm, characteristic of the Cu^{II} -phenolate interaction. This is lower than it was

observed in case of Cu^{II} -Phe-Tyr system (Fig. 3). It may be predicted that there is less involvement of phenolate group in the metal ion coordination.

Fig. 3. Visible spectra of Cu^{II} -Phe-Tyr (a) and Cu^{II} -Lys-Tyr (b) systems in 1 : 1 metal ion-dipeptide ratio at pH 9.4.

These results support that in solution, besides the side chain phenolate, the ϵ -amino group of lysyl in Lys-Tyr also plays a role in Cu^{II} ion binding. In dimers $[\text{Cu}_2\text{A}_2]$, both the lateral amino and the phenolate groups participate in the linking of $[\text{Cu}(\text{HAH}_{-1})]$ monomers. These results support that, under physiological conditions, the protonated Lys residue of metal-peptides may act as an 'anchor' for biological receptors^{12,13}.

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